

Experimental Verification of Pedagogical Conditions for Forming Schoolchildren's Aesthetic Taste in Out-of-School Education Institutions by Means of Dance

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Annotation. The article considers the task of studying the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, it was found that the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance in out-of-school education institutions as an integrated extracurricular educational activity allows for the interaction of two parties in a certain educational space, one of the components of which is pedagogical conditions. Therefore, in the process of organizing a certain specific pedagogical educational activity, for its effectiveness, it is necessary to create certain conditions for the implementation of this set of processes. The effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance was tested based on a pedagogical experiment (ascertaining and formative) as an empirical research method. Statistical analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment confirmed the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance: statistically significant positive dynamics were recorded for each indicator. In experimental groups of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions who took part in a pedagogical experiment of forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance, there is a dominance of high and medium levels of manifestation in all indicators (the general level of efficiency as a set of manifestations of all criteria). The results of the pedagogical experiment provide grounds for recommendations to out-of-school educational institutions to develop children's aesthetic taste by means of dance, in particular, ensuring regular training for advanced training of heads of dance studios, creation of a network for the exchange of experience between the heads of dance studios, which will contribute to the dissemination of successful development of the aesthetic taste of pupils; development of methodological recommendations and didactic video materials for

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conducting/accompanying classes for the formation of aesthetic taste of fashion through more effective organization of dance teaching.

Keywords: aesthetic taste, choreographic activity, schoolchildren, out-of-school education institution, dance, non-formal education.

Експериментальна перевірка педагогічних умов формування естетичного смаку школярів в закладах позашкільної освіти засобами танцю

Анотація. У статті подані результати дослідження ефективності організаційно-педагогічних умов формування естетичного смаку школярів в закладах позашкільної освіти засобами танцю. На основі аналізу психолого-педагогічної літератури було встановлено, що формування естетичного смаку школярів засобами танцю у закладах позашкільної освіти - це інтегрована позакласна освітня діяльність дозволяє здійснювати взаємодію двох сторін у певному освітньому просторі, однією зі складових якого є педагогічні умови. Ефективність педагогічних умов формування естетичного смаку школярів засобами танцю у закладах позашкільної освіти перевірялася на основі педагогічного експерименту (констатувальний і формувальний) як емпіричного дослідницького методу. Статистичний аналіз результатів педагогічного експерименту підтвердив ефективність педагогічних умов формування естетичного смаку школярів засобами танцю в закладах позашкільної освіти: зафіксовано статистично значущу позитивну динаміку за кожним із показників. В експериментальних групах школярів у закладах позашкільної освіти, які взяли участь у педагогічному експерименті, спостерігається домінування високого і середнього рівнів вияву за усіма показниками (загальний рівень ефективності як сукупність прояву усіх критеріїв). Результати педагогічного експерименту надають підстави для рекомендацій позашкільним освітнім установам щодо розвитку естетичного смаку вихованців засобами танцю, зокрема забезпечення регулярного проходження тренінгів для підвищення кваліфікації керівників танцювальних студій; створення мережі обміну досвідом між керівниками танцювальних студій, який сприятиме поширенню успішних практик розвитку естетичного смаку вихованців; розробка методичних рекомендацій та дидактичних відео-матеріалів для проведення/ супроводу занять для формування естетичного смаку.

Ключові слова: естетичний смак, хореографічна діяльність, школярі, заклад позашкільної освіти, танець, неформальна освіта.

Introduction

Problem statement. Humanization of the modern education system, which is focused on the development of the individual and the realization of his spiritual and aesthetic needs, requires a rethinking of the content of out-of-school education for schoolchildren.

In modern conditions of reforming the educational system, considerable attention is paid to the musical and aesthetic education of students by means of art, which is aimed at the formation of the child's spiritual world, his emotional sphere, the development of a sense of beauty, musical taste, and creativity. From the perspective of this issue, the problem of using dance means in the formation of aesthetic taste in out-of-school educational institutions needs to be investigated since involvement in participation in dance circles contributes to the aesthetic education of children, has a positive impact on their physical development, and contributes to the growth of their general culture [1]. The study's relevance is also determined

by the general decline in the interest of adolescents in the theoretical understanding of dance in aesthetic reality, as well as the need for more development of pedagogical technologies for musical and aesthetic education by means of dance.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In the psychological and pedagogical works of scientists K. Ushynsky, V. Sukhomlynsky, L. Vygotsky, N. Myropolska, O. Rudnytska, and others, children's aesthetic taste depends on their age characteristics. In adolescence, schoolchildren increase their activity and readiness for active actions. That is why schoolchildren are objectively interested in various improvisational dance compositions and various content of their choreographic activities [1; 4].

The process of improving the musical and aesthetic education of adolescents in the conditions of out-of-school education is studied by domestic and foreign scientists [5; 7; 8; 9; 11]. In scientific works, certain aspects of musical and aesthetic education are investigated. Modern scientific views on personality-oriented aesthetic education and the humanization of out-of-school education outline the problem of forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance as an integral part of the spiritual culture of the individual. The dominant dance and aesthetic activity of schoolchildren is their involvement in various forms of group work in out-of-school educational institutions, which stimulates the development of a creative personality. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, it was found that the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance in out-of-school education institutions as an integrated extracurricular educational activity allows for the interaction of two parties in a certain educational space, one of the components of which is pedagogical conditions. Therefore, in the process of organizing a certain specific pedagogical educational activity, for its effectiveness, it is necessary to create certain conditions for the implementation of this set of processes.

So, we considered the task of studying the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance.

The article aims to check the effectiveness of organizational and pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance.

Results

The study of the problem of the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by dancing in out-of-school education institutions requires the establishment of a cause-and-effect relationship and dependence, which manifests itself in the form of the main trends and determines the pedagogical conditions of this process [10]. We perceive "pedagogical conditions" as an important component of the educational activity of an out-of-school education institution, in which an educational environment is created for the aesthetic education of adolescents and ensuring the effective development of the thus, pedagogical conditions make a connection between the organization of the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in the conditions of an out-of-school educational institution and the provision of musical and aesthetic education by means of dance.

Since modern socio-cultural circumstances are constantly changing, there is a need to develop new pedagogical conditions for the effective formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren. Based on the study of practical pedagogical experience of out-of-school educational institutions and their educational potential, taking into account the requirements of regulatory state documents on education and the analysis of our own experience of pedagogical activity [2; 3; 5; 7], we have developed and substantiated the following pedagogical conditions that ensure the forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance:

- 1) motivating the heads of dance studios to pedagogical activities that ensure the consistent formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren through the creation of a positively trusting, hedonistically oriented aesthetic atmosphere of dance training;
- 2) enrichment of the aesthetic thesaurus of schoolchildren and their aesthetic experience through video lectures and educational meetings;
- 3) development of creative abilities of schoolchildren through improvisation, staging dances, and participation in concert activities.

When determining a person's musical and aesthetic education, one should consider the qualities that determine the value attitude to musical art, indicate the level of awareness and theoretical knowledge in musical and aesthetic education, and reflect an emotional attitude to music. Therefore, we have identified three main criteria for the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren: personal, creative-praxeological, and behavioral [6; 10]. For each of the criteria, indicators are determined (Fig. 1), and three levels of formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren are characterized: high, medium, and low.

Fig.1. Diagnostics of schoolchildren's aesthetic taste

The personal criterion assumes that the student has an interest/ motive in mastering his favorite dance works, a desire to participate in dance events, and a desire to be aware of the dance material from the point of view of its aesthetics, as well as mastering various types of dance activities. The indicator of this criterion is the attitude to aesthetic perception. The creative and praxeological criterion of the formation of schoolchildren's aesthetic taste characterizes the ability of students to operate with dance means and assess the aesthetic content of images in dance works. The third criterion for forming schoolchildren's aesthetic taste is productivity (which characterizes the degree of students' ability to participate in creative activity). It is important that schoolchildren can not only evaluate and choose a dance repertoire but also create and embody dance images in their performing activities.

The holistic application of the characterized criteria and indicators makes it possible to determine the levels of formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren (low, medium, high). At the same time, it is worth emphasizing that such differentiation according to the levels of formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren can be considered instead conditional and generalized because each of the criteria, according to certain indicators, requires differentiation according to the age parameters of pupils and taking into account the content of training depending on the year of mastering the art of dance. It should be emphasized that each mentor, based on the generalized criteria and indicators determined by us, has the opportunity to independently clarify the high, medium, and low levels of formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren as the acquired experience of mastering a choreographic, artistic model, taking into account the content of teaching choreography in their own program.

The developed criteria and indicators made it possible to differentiate the formation of aesthetic taste of schoolchildren at the qualitative level (description of the qualities of

schoolchildren with high, medium, and low levels of development of aesthetic taste) and the quantitative level after selection (the method of motivational induction by J. Newten) and the development of appropriate methods (Researcher's observation, Choreographic tasks) of their quantitative assessment.

The effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance was tested based on a pedagogical experiment (ascertaining and formative) as an empirical research method [6].

The ascertaining experiment was directly organized with the participation of a researcher (head of the Chinese and ballroom dance studio) and teachers of choreographic activities in out-of-school education institutions, as well as with the participation of ensembles and studios of folk and ballroom dance in Sumy and Sumy region. A total of 148 schoolchildren and 11 team leaders took part in it. The ascertaining experiment was conducted to determine schoolchildren's existing level of aesthetic taste. In particular, the level of knowledge of schoolchildren of the aesthetic thesaurus, their ability to perform the basic movements of folk or European and Latin American dances and analyze their aesthetics, the ability to distinguish the costumes of performers of folk or ballroom dances from the costumes of other dance genres and analyze their aesthetics, the ability to invite them to dance; the attitude of schoolchildren to aesthetics and choreographic art, the nature of schoolchildren's interest in aesthetic choreographic activities. The observation and survey revealed sufficient formation of students' theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the lexical language of dances. Therefore, the formation of aesthetic taste by means of dance will be more effective if the forms and methods of folk and ballroom dance classes are aimed at stimulating emotional-improvisational, psychophysical, and active-creative manifestations of schoolchildren. Also, most dance teachers noted the importance of forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance activities.

Later, at the formative stage of the pedagogical experiment, in the course of experimental research, we checked the pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance. The first pedagogical condition provided for preliminary training for the leaders of dance groups focused on acquaintance and mastery of methods for creating a trusting, hedonistically oriented aesthetic atmosphere of dance training. The second and pedagogical conditions were implemented within the framework of classes of dance groups in the conditions of out-of-school education.

After completing training to form the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance, the heads of dance studios, with our support, improved their own training programs, saturating them with video materials and creative tasks. We have developed a basic program, "Ballroom and Chinese Choreography," for out-of-school institutions. The program's content includes dances, which are divided into two groups in their style: European dances and Latin American dances, as well as dances created based on the national dance culture of China. Using a person-centered approach within the curriculum involves considering each pupil's characteristics, interests, abilities, and needs. Conditions were created for comprehensive personality development through dance, providing emotional comfort and stimulating self-development. The leader considered the level of training, physical and mental capabilities, interests, and emotional state of each pupil, adapting educational tasks and methods to his needs.

Thus, the formative experiment provided for the implementation of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance through the introduction of the author's model. The final stage of the pedagogical experiment was the verification of the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren by means of dance within the defined criteria.

In out-of-school education institutions (from several dance circles), control (CG, 64 people) and experimental (EG, 58 people) were formed. The age of the participants in the

pedagogical experiment varied from 13 to 16 years. The gender distribution for CG and EG was similar: 38% were boys, 62% were girls.

For statistical analysis, the methods of visual analysis and the Student's criterion for evaluating averages, which are calculated by the tools of the Excel spreadsheet processor (Analysis Package) [6], were used. To calculate the Student's criterion, the significance level of 0.05 and the null hypothesis of the zero difference of the means in CG and EG were chosen:

H0: $\mu_{EG} = \mu_{CG}$, that is, the averages are the same;

H_a: $\mu_{EG} \neq \mu_{CG}$, i.e., the averages are statistically different.

The methodology for statistical analysis of empirical data for each indicator was the same. The dynamics for each indicator before and after the experiment are shown in the table (Table 1) and figures (Fig. 2-4).

Table 1

Dynamics for each of the indicators

Indicator	Aesthetic taste level	EG	CG
Attitude to aesthetic perception	Low	-25,9%	-11,0%
	Medium	6,9%	3,1%
	High	19,0%	7,9%
Ability to carry out the aesthetic assessment	Low	-19,0%	-7,9%
	Medium	8,5%	3,2%
	High	10,5%	4,7%
Ability to creative activity to create dance images	Low	-22,4%	-12,5%
	Medium	1,7%	7,8%
	High	20,7%	4,7%

Fig.2. Indicator "Attitude to aesthetic perception"

Fig.3. Indicator "Ability to carry out aesthetic assessment"

Fig.4. Indicator "Ability to creative activity to create dance images"

Analytical comprehension of the experimental data obtained serves as a basis for the conclusion that the developed pedagogical conditions have yielded positive results. In experimental groups of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions who took part in a pedagogical experiment on the formation of aesthetic taste by means of dance, there is a dominance of high and medium levels of manifestation in all indicators (the general level of efficiency as a set of manifestations of all criteria).

The results of the pedagogical experiment provide grounds for recommendations to out-of-school educational institutions on the development of the aesthetic taste of pupils by means of dance:

- ensuring regular training to improve the skills of dance studio managers;
- creation of a network for the exchange of experience between the heads of dance studios, which will contribute to the dissemination of successful development of the aesthetic taste of pupils;
- development of methodological recommendations and didactic video materials for conducting/accompanying classes to form the aesthetic taste of fashion through a more effective dance teaching organization.

Conclusions

Thus, we have experimentally confirmed the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance. For this purpose, a diagnostic apparatus of research was developed: criteria and indicators for the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren – personal (attitude to aesthetic perception), creative-praxeological (ability to carry out aesthetic assessment), productive (ability to creative activity to create dance images), which made it possible level differentiation (high, medium, low) of the formation of the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren.

Statistical analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment confirmed the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for forming the aesthetic taste of schoolchildren in out-of-school education institutions by means of dance: statistically significant positive dynamics were recorded for each indicator.

The completed research only exhausts some aspects of the research problem. Other research areas remain open to improving the model of the formation of aesthetic taste by means of dance in the conditions of out-of-school education.

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